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A high-sensitivity low-cost digital ^1H and ^{129}Xe NMR spectrometer operating in the mT field regime

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ABSTRACT

This work presents the development of a Spin-Exchange Optical Pumping (SEOP) system for hyperpolarizing xenon (Xe) isotopes, coupled to an ultra-low-field Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) prototype capable of detecting NMR signals up to 200 kHz. The system enables polarization measurements of stable Xe isotopes and offers a compact, cost-effective solution for low-field NMR applications.

The NMR prototype integrates RF coils, a digital acquisition board, and a graphical user interface (UI). An RF excitation at the Larmor frequency is generated, and the corresponding relaxation signals are acquired. The digital board incorporates an FPGA, microcontroller, and embedded memory, with USB and Ethernet interfaces for real-time data transfer.

A current-controlled Helmholtz coil was engineered to produce a uniform static magnetic field (B_0) across the region of interest. To enhance the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), separate transmitter and receiver coils were used. The receiver coil was designed with a high turn count and an optimized quality factor (Q).

The main challenge of this work was the nanovolt-level NMR signal. Ultra-low-noise analog front-end electronics, combined with optimized PCB layout and extensive electromagnetic shielding, were employed. Advanced signal processing techniques, including synchronized switching, filtering, and signal averaging, enabled reliable signal detection in the millitesla (mT) regime.

Experimental validation using ^1H and ^{129}Xe NMR confirmed the system’s capability to acquire signals in the kHz range, demonstrating its potential for portable, low cost and low-field NMR applications.

INDEX TERMS Digital NMR Spectrometer, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance NMR, Spin Exchange Optical Pumping (SEOP), Ultra-Low Magnetic Field, Tunable Circuits, Analog Low Noise Amplification, Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) circuits

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there had been growing interest in low-field Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) applications due to lower maintenance costs and simplified operational requirements. Unlike conventional high-field systems that require superconducting magnets, low-field NMR/MRI systems eliminate the need for cryogenics, thus reducing both infrastructure demands and safety concerns. These advantages make low-field NMR/MRI a promising alternative for broader applications, including portable diagnostics and cost-effective solutions [1], [2], [3], [4].

Despite these advantages, low-field NMR systems face significant challenges, particularly in achieving sufficient signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) due to the inherently weaker magnetization at lower magnetic fields [5], [6].

To address these limitations, hyperpolarization techniques such as Spin Exchange Optical Pumping (SEOP) have been employed to enhance nuclear spin polarization, thereby significantly improving signal detectability [7], [8], [9], [10]. This study focuses on the development of a compact and ultra-sensitive SEOP system, and an NMR spectrometer optimized for low-field applications. The proposed system is designed to operate within the milli Tesla (mT) range, capable of detecting NMR signals at frequencies up to 200 kHz. Specifically, the study explores the polarization and detection of both ^1H (protons) and hyperpolarized ^{129}Xe using an ultra-low-field NMR setup.

The NMR system consists of a custom-built SEOP setup, including Helmholtz coils generating magnetic fields up to 6.5 mT, a thermo-insulating oven with water cooling, and a 50 W laser for optical pumping of Rb-Xe gas mixtures. A dedicated NMR detection system, comprising two Helmholtz-like transmitter coils and a Litz wire RF receiver coil, calibrated to resonate at the appropriate Larmor frequencies. Specific electronic boards have been developed for this application, including an ultra-low-noise analog amplification, a digital electronic incorporating a high-speed analog-to-digital converter, an FPGA, a microcontroller and on-board memory, not forgetting Ethernet and USB interfaces for real-time data acquisition.

A key challenge in ultra-low-field NMR is isolating the weak free induction decay (FID) signal from background noise. While previous studies [15],[17],[19],[20] have proposed various solutions including active feedback mechanisms and optimized detection resonators, a comprehensive approach for achieving robust signal detection in the sub-10 mT field range remains lacking.

To bridge this gap, our system incorporates different coils optimized for its function, a free-running oscillation reduction technique, ultra-low-noise amplification as well as optimized shielding techniques and advanced noise reduction strategies to improve detection sensitivity.

The objective of this study is to develop and validate an efficient low-field NMR system, capable of measuring the polarization of ^1H and stable Xe isotopes. By addressing key limitations in low-field signal detection, this work contributes to the advancement of portable and cost-effective NMR technologies for broader scientific applications.

II. COILS DESIGN

In this work, three distinct groups of coils were developed for the NMR system: A pair of Helmholtz coils for B_0 generation, a pair of transmitter coils for B_1 excitation and a receiver coil for the NMR signal detection.

II.A. Helmholtz coils for B_0 generation

The Helmholtz coil pair, shown in **FIGURE 1**, is designed to generate the external static magnetic field B_0 . The field strength is adjustable from 0.1 to 6.5 mT, regulated by a BK Precision 9183B current source with a range of 0 to 6 A in the 0 to 35 volt range, and an accuracy of 850 μA (corresponding to $1.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mT).

The required number of turns n to achieve the desired B_0 was calculated using the formula (1):

$$B_0 = \frac{\mu_0 \cdot n \cdot I}{R} \cdot \left(\frac{4}{5}\right)^{3/2} \quad (1)$$

Where B_0 is the magnetic field (T), μ_0 is the vacuum magnetic permeability ($\text{kg} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2} \cdot \text{A}^{-2}$), n the number of turns (-), I the applied current (A) and R is the radius of the coil (m). Setting the distance between the Helmholtz coils pair equal to the radius of the coil, one can minimize the nonuniformity of the field at the center of the coils.

Each Helmholtz coil has 400 mm diameter, 345 turns, and is separated by 200 mm. The copper wire used has a diameter of 1.6 mm to minimize resistance and power dissipation. No active cooling was needed, as heat generation remained within acceptable limits. The relationship between the applied current and the resulting B_0 -field was experimentally characterized, and the measured data are presented in **FIGURE 2**.

This configuration results in the creation of a quasi-constant B_0 magnetic field at the geometrical center, where the sample of interest is positioned.

FIGURE 1. Helmholtz coils (1) with, in the center, the SEOP glass cell and SEOP oven (2)

FIGURE 2. B_0 field as a function of applied current at the center of the Helmholtz coil

To assess the magnetic field uniformity, spatial mapping was performed using a Hall probe mounted on an XYZ translation stage, with a spatial resolution of 1 mm within a 3 cm spherical region at the coil center. The field distribution was analyzed using spherical harmonics expansion [18], a method that provides a quantitative representation of spatial field inhomogeneity and allows for identification of dominant sources of distortion. Measurements were conducted with a fixed current of 2.81 A, corresponding to $B_0=4.5$ mT.

The magnetic field $B(r,\theta,\phi)$ was expressed using a spherical harmonic (2):

$$B(r, \theta, \phi) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l C_{lm} Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi) \quad (2)$$

Where $Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi)$ are the spherical harmonic functions, and C_{lm} are experimentally determined coefficients in ppm.

The field deviations were:

$$C_{1,0} = -50.10, C_{1,1} = 230.3, C_{1,-1} = -946.9$$

$$C_{2,0} = -1053, C_{2,1} = 129.9, C_{2,2} = -14.56, C_{2,-1} = -38.20,$$

$$C_{2,-2} = 1.118$$

$$C_{3,0} = -83.88, C_{3,1} = 24.96, C_{3,2} = 1.342, C_{3,3} = -8.191,$$

$$C_{3,-1} = -43.20, C_{3,-2} = 0.633, C_{3,-3} = 8.316$$

These results indicate that the quadrupole term ($l = 2$) is the dominant source of inhomogeneity, contributing a maximum deviation of 1053 ppm. The dipole term ($l = 1$) also introduces a significant inhomogeneity of 50 ppm along the same axis, suggesting the presence of a linear gradient along B_0 .

Higher order distortions ($l = 3$) were minimal, indicating that contributions beyond the second order have a limited impact on the overall field homogeneity.

The total spectral linewidth measured on the FID FFT ($\Delta f_{total} \approx 250$ Hz, see FIGURE 15 and FIGURE 16) can be viewed as the quadrature sum of two independent contributions, Equation (3), field-inhomogeneity broadening (Δf_{inhom}) and intrinsic transverse-decay broadening ($\Delta f_{intrinsic}$) [24]:

$$\Delta f_{total}^2 = \Delta f_{inhom}^2 + \Delta f_{intrinsic}^2 \quad (3)$$

For ^1H , considering only the field inhomogeneity along the B_0 axis (i.e., the $m = 0$ terms), the field-induced broadening is, Equation (4):

$$\Delta f_{inhom, axis} (^1\text{H}) = \sqrt{\sum_{\ell=1}^3 \left(\frac{\gamma\text{H}}{2\pi} B_0 \frac{|C_{\ell,0}|}{10^6} \right)^2} \quad (4)$$

$$\approx \sqrt{(9.6)^2 + (202)^2 + (16)^2} \approx 203 \text{ Hz}$$

$$\Delta f_{intrinsic} (^1\text{H}) = \sqrt{250^2 - 203^2} \approx 150 \text{ Hz}$$

Where m is the azimuthal order ($-$), $C_{\ell,0}$ are the spherical harmonic coefficients (ppm) associated with the inhomogeneity components aligned along the B_0 axis, and $\frac{\gamma}{2\pi}$ is the gyromagnetic ratio of the nucleus of interest expressed in Hz/T.

Thus, of the 250 Hz FWHM observed for protons, ~ 203 Hz arises from gradients collinear with B_0 and ~ 150 Hz from true transverse decay. Such a total broadening (< 300 Hz) remains fully compatible with the spectral-resolution requirements of ultra-low-field NMR, where chemical-shift separations and Tr measurements typically span a few hundred hertz.

Because ^{129}Xe has a lower gyromagnetic ratio ($\frac{\gamma}{2\pi} \approx 11.78 \text{ MHz/T}$), the same ppm distribution yields only ($\Delta f_{\text{inhom,axis}}(^{129}\text{Xe}) \approx 56 \text{ Hz}$) so that the intrinsic term dominates ($\Delta f_{\text{intrinsic}}(^{129}\text{Xe}) \approx \sqrt{250^2 - 56^2} \approx 244 \text{ Hz}$). As a result, our Helmholtz-coil system's field uniformity is even more than sufficient for hyperpolarized ^{129}Xe NMR experiments.

These findings demonstrate that the Helmholtz coil system provides a reasonably uniform magnetic field within the studied volume.

FIGURE 3. B_0 -field evolution (top), temperature at the center of the coil pair measured by a Hall probe (middle), and Helmholtz coil temperature (bottom) as a function of time

As shown in **FIGURE 3** the measured data illustrate the evolution of the Helmholtz coil pair's magnetic field, the Hall probe readings at the sample position, and the Helmholtz coil temperature evolution. The results indicate that for a temperature variation of 0.5°C , the magnetic field fluctuates by only $1 \mu\text{T}$, demonstrating the stability of B_0 under operational conditions.

Additionally, a thermocouple placed directly on the Helmholtz coils monitored temperature variations during extended system operation. The recorded data indicate that the coil temperature increased from 21°C to 29°C , reaching a plateau after approximately four hours. Despite this temperature rise, the effect on the ambient temperature was minimal, as the system operates in a large-volume environment helping to dissipate excess heat.

At the center of the Helmholtz coils, the sample may include doped H_2O , hyperpolarized Xe , or any other isotopes that exhibit Larmor frequencies in the kHz regime. In **FIGURE 5a** one can observe a 3D model representing a spherical phantom 1 housing the sample, positioned at the middle of two RF transmitter coils 2, mounted on a custom-made plastic support alongside one receiver coil 3.

II.B. Receiver and transmitter coils

Two transmitter coils generate a B_1 oscillating magnetic field, perpendicular to the B_0 static field as shown in **FIGURE 5a**. Using the same generic formula (1), we designed the coils to generate a magnetic field up to $100 \mu\text{T}$ Root-Mean-Square (RMS). Each coil is made of seven turns of copper wire and has a diameter of 65 mm . The total resistance of the two coils is approximately $250 \text{ m}\Omega$ at 20°C .

To calculate the total inductance value L (μH) for the two coils, we used the following empirical Equation (5):

$$L = 2 \cdot \frac{10 \cdot \pi \cdot N^2 \cdot R_1^2}{6 \cdot R_1 + 9 \cdot l + 10 \cdot (R_2 - R_1)} \quad (5)$$

Where N is the number of turns (-), R_1 the internal radius (m), R_2 the external radius (m) and l the winding width (m), all these of which correspond to a single coil.

This results in an inductance of $13.1 \mu\text{H}$ for the coil and an ideal quality factor Q of about 17.5 at the 53 kHz Larmor frequency, calculated using Equation (6).

$$Q = \frac{2\pi f L}{R} \quad (6)$$

From an electronic perspective, the transmitter coil was initially designed to operate in an LC-type resonant configuration, using L_c and C_c (**FIGURE 7**). However, because the magnetic field B_1 required in our experiments is extremely low, operating the coil at resonance did not allow precise control of the generated field amplitude.

Therefore, the transmitter coil is intentionally operated off resonance, i.e., not tuned to the Larmor frequency. With the selected values of L_c and C_c , the coil's resonance frequency lies well away from the Larmor frequency.

To ensure accurate control of the magnetic field B_1 (one of the key parameter adjusted during system tuning), the amplitude and frequency of the excitation signal are directly set via the digitally controlled sine-wave generator (see **FIGURE 7**).

Operating the transmitter coil in a non-resonant mode also provides a faster decay of the transmitted RF signal when switching to the NMR detection phase. This behavior facilitates improved detection of the NMR signal, which could otherwise be partially masked by the longer ring-down time characteristic of a resonant system.

Using Equations (1), (5), (6) an independent receiver coil was designed to measure the emitted NMR signal. It is placed beneath the phantom at a 90 -degree angle to the transmitter coil (**FIGURE 5a**).

The receiver coil consists of 250 turns of Litz wire, with a cross-sectional area of 0.236 mm^2 and is composed of 30 copper strands, each with a diameter of 0.1 mm . The coil has an outer diameter of 6 cm , an inner diameter of 6 mm and a

thickness approximately 7 mm. Its inductance and resistance are approximately 2.6 mH and 13.1 Ω respectively. The theoretical quality factor Q is around 66.

The resonance capacitor is adjusted (C_r in **FIGURE 8**), with a value close to 3.7 nF.

The **FIGURE 4** depicts the measured forward transmission coefficient S_{21} of the receiver coil: we can deduce a quality factor of 44.6, which is slightly below the calculated theoretical value.

FIGURE 4. Forward transmission coefficient S_{21} for the receiver coil

The coil is designed so that the sample can be positioned as close to it as possible to maximize signal detection. A tuned capacitor C_r is connected in parallel with the receiver coil to achieve resonance at the Larmor frequency. Thanks to its intrinsic properties, Litz wire enhances the quality factor of the LC circuit compared to traditional copper wire, improving NMR signal capture.

The decision to use two independent coils, one for generating the B_1 field pulses and the other for receiving the emitted RF signals (containing the NMR signal), was made to allow independent optimization of each coil for its specific function. This approach is particularly beneficial for the receiver coil, which requires a high-quality factor (Q) and a higher number of turns to amplify the received signal and improve the signal-to-noise SNR ratio.

Regarding the mutual inductance between the transmitter and receiver coils, we ensured that the mechanical supports for the coils were positioned as orthogonally as possible. A final positioning adjustment was made, using a magnetic field probe, to minimize this effect.

As discussed later in the section on ^1H and ^{129}Xe measurements, the same Larmor frequency was used for both cases. To achieve this, the magnetic fields B_0 and B_1 were adjusted to maintain a consistent configuration for the receiver coil and the resonance capacitors.

FIGURE 5.

a) The glass cell (1), B_1 B_1 transmitter coils (2) and the receiver coil (3)
b) The NMR setup comprising the Helmholtz coils for B_0 (1), the transmitter coils (2), the receiver coil (3) and a cylindrical glass cell (4)

II.C. Setting of the B_1 field

The B_1 field is configured to achieve a flip angle α of 90° , which is optimal for maximizing the detected NMR signal. The flip angle (in degrees) is given by the following Equation (7):

$$\alpha = 360 \cdot B_1 \cdot \gamma \cdot T_e \quad (7)$$

Where, B_1 represents the Root Mean Square (RMS) value of the magnetic field (T), T_e is the duration of the transmission pulse (s) at the Larmor frequency and γ is the gyromagnetic ratio of the nuclei ($\text{Hz} \cdot \text{T}^{-1}$).

To configure the flip angle, our system allows for the adjustment of either the B_1 field intensity or the duration of the T_e pulse duration (see **FIGURE 7**).

III. ELECTRONICS DESIGN

FIGURE 6 illustrates the schematic diagram of the electronic system for the transmitter signal and the NMR signal reception.

At the core of this design is an in-house digital electronic board developed by our team at HEPIA, named CORE1. This board integrates a Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) circuit, a microcontroller, a 512 MB Double Data Rate (DDR) dynamic memory, Ethernet and USB interfaces. The CORE1 board is designed to facilitate data acquisition, storage, and transfer to a PC.

For this specific application, a custom mezzanine board, named CAB, has been developed. The CORE1 board is inserted into the CAB board, which is equipped with electronics to generate the required current for producing the B_1 excitation magnetic field via the transmitter coils.

FIGURE 6. Schematic diagram of the complete NMR electronic system [25]

The system also manages the acquisition and conditioning of the NMR signal received from the receiver coil.

The transmitter consists of a sinusoidal signal generator with programmable frequency and amplitude covering the range of Larmor frequencies corresponding to the nuclei of interest (here ^1H and ^{129}Xe). Additionally, an amplifier supplies the required current to the transmitter coils for generating B_1 . A fast-switching circuit generate the transmit sequence during T_e and the stop sequence during the T_r (FIGURE 7). Furthermore, it integrates a selectable capacitor bank that enables tuning of the resonant frequency of the $C_e - L_e$ pair. For the receiver (FIGURE 8), a similar capacitor bank (C_r) is used, adjusted based on the inductance of the receive coil (L_r) and the Larmor frequency. Special consideration has been given to the selection of operational amplifiers, as the received signal has an extremely low amplitude. To maximize the SNR ratio, high-performance components were chosen.

The amplification chain consists of three stages, achieving a total gain of up to 10^6 . This gain is distributed across multiple amplifiers to avoid bandwidth limitations within the system. Additionally, low-pass and high-pass filters are applied to the signal before it undergoes digital sampling and conversion. The signal is digitized using a 10-bit Flash analog-to-digital (A/D) converter, capable of sampling up to 40 mega samples/s (MS/s). However, for this application, the sampling rate was limited to 1 MS/s, as the Larmor frequencies remain below 100 kHz.

III.A. RF Transmitter electronics

Our approach is inspired by the insights from publications [19] and [20], with the foundational principle illustrated in FIGURE 7. It features a sinusoidal generator that enables the configuration of the setpoint signal, allowing adjustments to frequency, amplitude and the T_e and T_r durations. Alongside the transmitted signal, there is a SYNC output which provides the synchronization signal.

FIGURE 7. Transmitter RF pulses electronic circuit principle [25]

The SYNC signal is used to control the Q_1 and Q_2 switches as well as the switches Q_3 and Q_4 switches of the receiver circuit (FIGURE 8).

The arrangement is critical, as the receiver coil needs to be detuned from the Larmor frequency during the transmit phase (T_e). Conversely, during the receive phase (T_r), the transmitter coil needs to be detuned while the receiver coil is tuned to the Larmor frequency for effective signal reception.

More precisely, during the transmit phase (T_e), the magnetic field B_1 , oscillating at the Larmor frequency, is transmitted through the coils. During this phase, switch Q_1 is closed, and Q_2 is opened. The Larmor frequency and the voltage amplitude, i-e proportionally the B_1 field, are precisely adjusted (by measuring B_1 with a field probe at the location where the phantom will be placed). Once the transmit phase ends, and the receive phase (T_r) begins, the positions of switches Q_1 and Q_2 are reversed: Q_1 is opened, and Q_2 is closed which short-circuits the coil to ground or via the C_a capacitor. This rapidly detunes the coil from the Larmor frequency, preventing further resonance and ensuring that no B_1 magnetic field is applied during the T_r period. During this phase, it is critical to eliminate any interference that could affect NMR signal reception. The maximum current (I_{max}) in the transmitter coils is regulated based on the B_1 magnetic field, calculated using Equation (1) in Section II.

III.B. NMR receiver electronics

The **FIGURE 8** illustrates the schematic diagram of the electronic architecture of the NMR signal reception.

FIGURE 8. NMR signal receiver electronic circuit principle [25]

NMR signal reception represents the most critical aspect of the system, requiring meticulous attention to component selection, power supply filtering, and designing the PCB layout to minimize electronic noise. The main challenge lies in the exceptionally low amplitude of the NMR signal, which is on the order of a few nanovolts (nV).

To address this, a three-stage operational amplifier chain, featuring the SSM2019 operational amplifier (AOP) was implemented. The SSM2019 is known for its very low noise level, typically $1.7 \text{ nV}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 1 kHz for a gain of 100. Its exceptional noise characteristics are partly achieved by operating its input transistors at high collector currents, as voltage noise is inversely proportional to the square root of the collector current. The SSM2019 operational amplifier was selected for its excellent intrinsic voltage noise performance, superior to FET-input amplifiers. Although bipolar devices exhibit higher current noise levels, the effective impedance seen at the amplifier input during operation is significantly reduced by the resonant detection network and associated parasitic capacitances at the Larmor frequency. As a result, the contribution of current noise to the overall noise voltage is negligible under our experimental conditions. The use of a bipolar amplifier also ensures high stability and power supply rejection, which are critical for our high-Q resonant configuration.

The total noise can be calculated using Equation (8):

$$E_n = \sqrt{e_n^2 + e_t^2 + (R_s \cdot i_n)^2} \quad (8)$$

Where $E_n = 1.7 \text{ nV}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 1 kHz (total input-referred noise), $e_n = 1.7 \text{ nV}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 1 kHz (amplifier voltage noise), $i_n = 0.002 \text{ nA}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 1 kHz (amplifier current noise), $R_s = 0.88 \text{ } \Omega$ (receiver coil resistance) and e_t (source resistance thermal noise) is negligible. This low total noise level (E_n) ensures that the SSM2019 is almost uninfluential as a noise contributor.

Special attention must be paid to the surroundings of the receive coil, as even minimal electromagnetic noise could saturate the amplification chain, making the NMR signal undetectable.

To mitigate environmental noise interference, several measures were implemented: general shielding of the electronic system using an aluminum enclosure encapsulation of the NMR signal amplification stage within a shielded area (**FIGURE 9**, **FIGURE 11**), common-mode filtering of power supplies, shielded twisted-pair cable used from the coil to the analog input for the receive NMR signal, ferrite beads applied to the power supply cables to suppress high-frequency noise and careful PCB design including multilayer routing techniques to minimize interference. Additionally, separate power supplies were used for the transmit and receive boards, ensuring they are not connected to the same equipotential ground point.

The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of inductive NMR detection scales approximately as SNR proportional to $B_0^{7/4}$ under coil-noise-limited conditions. According to this relationship, increasing B_0 from 1.245 mT to 4.5 mT (see chapter V. RESULTS) would theoretically yield an SNR gain of about 9.5 ($\approx +19.5 \text{ dB}$), illustrating the expected sensitivity trade-off of our fixed-frequency / variable B_0 approach.

The spectrometer was validated under the most unfavorable conditions, using ^1H , which requires the smallest B_0 and thus the lowest SNR. Despite this, detectable NMR signals were obtained. For ^{129}Xe , the gas employed for SEOP, the achievable SNR is expected to be nearly an order of magnitude higher under similar conditions.

The $B_0^{7/4}$ scaling represents an idealized limit where coil thermal noise dominates. In practice, additional contributions from sample losses, electronics, or coil geometry may attenuate this dependence. Nonetheless, operating at fixed frequency provides key practical advantages, i.e., simpler electronics, improved field stability, and faster RF ring-down, essential for robust low-field NMR operation.

In addition, the complete system as described in **FIGURE 1** is placed in a Faraday cage.

Additionally, signal averaging can be performed by the system, further increasing the SNR ratio.

FIGURE 9. Aluminum shielding on PCB to protect amplification chain from external electronic noise

A three-stage amplification system was implemented to maintain sufficient bandwidth. With a single stage amplifier, the required gain (G) would have been between $5 \cdot 10^5$ and 10^6 (as specified later in this section). Given a typical gain-bandwidth product (GBW) of 20 MHz, the cut-off frequency (f_c) would have been between 20 and 40 Hz, as calculated using Equation (9).

$$f_c = \frac{GBW}{G} \quad (9)$$

By distributing the total gain over 3 stages, with a maximum gain per stage of 100, the bandwidth is maintained at a minimum value of 200 kHz, which is in line with the Larmor frequency range to be measured.

The operation of the NMR signal can be described as follows: the SYNC synchronization signal is sent to the receiver circuit, enabling the short-circuiting of the receiver coil to ground, via the switches Q_3 and Q_4 during the T_e transmitter phase.

During the T_r phase, switches Q_3 and Q_4 are open allowing the receiver coil to resonate with the capacitor C_r . This resonance has its peak at the Larmor frequency. The selection of C_r was made to match this frequency.

An adjustable dead time zone (damped oscillation mask time) between 100 μ s and 1 ms, set at 400 μ s during the experimental validation, has been added (as shown in FIGURE 8) to avoid a significant voltage spike during the transition between T_e and T_r phases. The Q_3 and Q_4 switches are finely tuned to prevent immediate saturation ensuring T_e / T_r transition as smooth as possible.

Subsequently, the voltage across the receiver coil undergoes amplification through 3 adjustable gain stages. In our experiments, a total gain of $5 \cdot 10^5$ and 10^6 was used, although it is possible to reach a maximum gain of 10^6 . Both high-pass and low-pass filters are employed to filter out unwanted frequencies.

III.C. The complete NMR system

To create a fully integrated NMR system, which generates, receives, and acquires the NMR signal using the CORE1 and CAB boards, a PC is incorporated for data collection and visualization. This setup utilizes advanced tools for data display and system parameter configuration, with MATLAB® being an example of such tool. This results in a compact all-in-one system.

The fully integrated system is illustrated in FIGURE 10, FIGURE 11 and FIGURE 12. A LattePanda® PC interfaces with CORE1 via a USB connection. The system requires only a single main power supply, as all necessary voltages for system operation are generated directly on the CAB board. The transmit and receive coils are connected via BNC connectors, while a keyboard and mouse are connected through USB ports. Additionally, a monitor can be attached via an HDMI port, completing the setup. The dimensions of the case (FIGURE 12) are 103 mm x 130 mm x 53mm (width x length x height).

FIGURE 10. View of the designed PCB

FIGURE 11. Front PCB with the shielded acquisition electronics

FIGURE 12 Back PCB, LattePanda Mini PC. The whole system in compact case

FIGURE 13. User Interface

IV. USER INTERFACE (UI)

The control interface of the NMR system allows users to adjust parameters, enhancing the flexibility and precision of NMR experiments (FIGURE 13). The sequence of operations is illustrated in FIGURE 14.

The configurable parameters include:

- Sinusoidal frequency (Larmor frequency)
- Time between pulses (T_r)
- Transmitter coil voltage (B_1 field strength)
- Pulse duration (T_e)

Additionally, the acquisition parameters of the NMR system can be modified to customize data collection after stimulation. These parameters, accessible via the User Interface (UI), include:

- Recording time after the pulse
- Damped oscillation mask time (see FIGURE 14)
- Mean or continuous measurements modes
- RF sweep

Following acquisition of the NMR signal, the user application processes the amplified raw signal from the time domain to the frequency domain using the Fast Fourier Transforms (FFTs) algorithm. The UI software then displays the FFT representations, allowing for frequency analysis of the acquired NMR signals.

FIGURE 13 illustrates a typical example of such a measurement, displaying both the raw data and its

corresponding frequency-domain analysis. An NMR signal at 53.1 kHz was successfully observed. It illustrates the comparison of the FFT spectra with (in blue) and without (in yellow) the constant B_0 applied, that correspond to polarized and non-polarized ^1H respectively.

FIGURE 14. Sequence diagram

The FPGA-based control system developed in this work supports the programming of multiple pulse sequences. The user can define the number of pulses, the inter-pulse delays, the repetition rate, and the dead time duration with high timing precision. These features enable the implementation of a wide range of pulse experiments beyond single-pulse excitation.

V. RESULTS

The experimental validation of the system was initially conducted by measuring NMR signals from ^1H in a water sample containing CuSO_4 . The sample was prepared with CuSO_4 concentration of 50 mmol in 500 ml of water. Measurements were performed in a static magnetic field $B_0=1.25$ mT, corresponding to a Larmor frequency of 53.2 kHz.

The addition of CuSO_4 reduced both the longitudinal relaxation time (T_1) and the transverse relaxation time (T_2) the protons (^1H) in water. This reduction enabled a decrease in the interval between pulses, thereby reducing the total acquisition time and improving the SNR [21] and [22].

An initial FFT measurement is performed, in each experimental validation, without activating the B_0 magnetic field. This, of course, contains no NMR signal and corresponds to the basic reference measure, considering electromagnetic noise and any additional signals picked up (such as the non-orthogonal positioning of the transmitter and receiver coils).

The signal transmission and acquisition parameters for the ^1H NMR measurements were as follows:

- Sinusoidal Larmor Frequency: 53.2 kHz
- Static magnetic field B_0 : 1.25 mT
- Excitation RF field B_1 : 30 μT
- Pulse duration T_e : 190 μs
- Time between pulses T_r : 300 ms
- Number of consecutive T_e/T_r sequence: 300
- Recording time after pulse: 10 ms
- Damped oscillation mask time: 400 μs

The ^1H NMR spectrum acquired under Boltzmann distribution conditions, is shown in **FIGURE 15**.

FIGURE 15. ^1H FFT NMR signal of a water sample doped with CuSO_4

The NMR spectrum was fitted using a Lorentzian function with a linear background, given by the Equation (10):

$$S(x) = \frac{A}{\pi} \cdot \frac{\sigma}{(x-\mu)^2 + \sigma^2} + (ax + b) \quad (10)$$

Where A is the amplitude, μ is the resonance frequency, σ is the linewidth, and a and b represent the slope and intercept of the linear background, respectively.

FIGURE 15 illustrates the comparison of the NMR spectra recorded with B_0 applied (blue) and without B_0 (orange) magnetic field. These spectra correspond to polarized and non-polarized ^1H respectively.

A subsequent validation experiment was carried out using stable ^{129}Xe gas enclosed in a spherical glass cell. The static magnetic field B_0 and the field B_1 have been changed so that the Larmor frequency is the same than in the previous experiment. The ^{129}Xe was hyperpolarized via SEOP while positioned at the center of a static magnetic field $B_0=4.5$ mT. The NMR system detected an increase in the NMR signal due to hyperpolarization, demonstrating its capability to detect changes in signal strength before and after hyperpolarization. The signal transmission and acquisition parameters for the ^{129}Xe NMR measurements are the following:

- Sinusoidal Larmor Frequency: 53.2 kHz
- Static magnetic field B_0 : 4.5 mT
- Excitation RF field B_1 : 62 μT
- Pulse duration T_e : 345 μs
- Time between pulses T_r : 60 s
- Number of consecutive T_e/T_r sequence: 10
- Recording time after pulse: 10 ms
- Damped oscillation mask time: 400 μs

The ^{129}Xe NMR spectra acquired with SEOP (blue) and without SEOP (orange) at a static magnetic field $B_0=4.5$ mT are shown in **FIGURE 16**.

FIGURE 16. ^{129}Xe NMR NMR signal with (blue) and without (orange) hyperpolarization via SEOP

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have developed and validated a compact, low cost, highly sensitive NMR system capable of operating in very low magnetic fields (B_0).

The system was successfully tested through ^1H NMR signals from CuSO_4 -doped water at 53.2 kHz, as well as the detection of hyperpolarized ^{129}Xe under SEOP conditions.

The compact design of the system enhances its integration into various experimental environments, making it a promising tool for polarization measurements of stable Xe isotopes. Its ability to operate in ultra-low B_0 fields paves the way for portable, low-field NMR and spectroscopy applications.

Despite the advancements during this work, certain limitations remain. Notably the SNR, that could be further optimized through advanced RF coil design and noise reduction techniques. Furthermore, the current system operates within a limited frequency range, requiring hardware modifications to support the detection of other isotopes for broader applications.

To further enhance the system's capabilities, future research will focus on improving the detection sensitivity through advanced shielding and optimization of RF coil geometries.

Coil alignment corrections, additional compensation coils, or fine-tuning of the current distribution, could further enhance and optimize field uniformity of the Helmholtz coil.

Furthermore, the incorporation of real-time data processing and automation will improve acquisition efficiency and data analysis. Last, the adaptation of the system's design for multi-nuclei detection will enable polarization measurements of other xenon isotopes and beyond.

All electronic schematics, the bill of materials including the components cost, and board layouts have been made publicly available via GitHub [25]. The total cost of the entire system, including the PC, is around 800\$. The practical implementation of the figures discussed in Section III can be accessed through the same repository.

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TABLE 1. Nomenclature

FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
SEOP	Spin Exchange Optical Pumping
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
PET	Positron Emission Tomography
RMS	Root Mean Square
FWHM	Full Width at Half Maximum
CORE1	Digital board developed by HEPIA
CAB	Customer Application Board HEPIA
EM	Electromagnetic

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